

Green New Deal Simulator

Developed by: Molleindustria

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Keywords

Climate-change Education, Climate Policy Education, Democratic Values, Ecology, Economics, Energy Consumption, Environmental Law, Land-use Planning, Natural Disasters, Political Science, Pollution, Renewable Energy, Sustainability, Systems Thinking

Introduction

Figure 1. Official logo of Green New Deal Simulator, developed by Molleindustria (2023). All rights remain with the developer.

Green New Deal Simulator (see Figure 1) is a short activist game released in 2023 by the game studio Molleindustria to promote clean energy practices across the U.S. The game illustrates the difficulties of transitioning a fossil-fuel-dependent energy grid to clean, renewable energy (Couture, 2023). Players view a regional map of the United States and draw and play cards to interact with the game system. They must balance factors such as unemployment, the effectiveness of a given green energy technology for a particular region, politics, and more. They are given a finite amount of time to reach full green energy in each region of the U.S., with multiple negative random events that can set back the player's progress. Gameplay communicates both the pitfalls and benefits of attempting to reach zero carbon emissions

through relying entirely on green energy and explores the challenges of green energy conversion. It also showcases the highly complex system of energy politics, employment, finances, and public perception, allowing students to experience these hardships in a way that helps them better understand the causes and effects of each choice.

Facts

Release date:	May 1, 2023
Developer:	Molleindustria
Game type:	Digital
Number of players:	Single player
Format:	Asynchronous
Time frame:	20–30 minutes
Languages:	English
Environment:	Smartphones, tablets, Mac, or Windows PC
Material:	N/A
Price:	Available for free on itch.io.

Resonance & Criticism

Green New Deal Simulator has a Very Positive rating on Steam (87%) and a 4.4 out of 5 on the App Store as of 2025. The game continues to incite discussion about the effectiveness of green-based politics and solutions to the current climate crisis (Serin, 2023).

Critics reviewed the game positively on Gamedeveloper (Couture, 2023), Medium (Tecson, 2024), and Rock Paper Shotgun (Serin, 2023). Serin (2023) asserts that the game was a fun lesson that gamifies a serious topic and breaks it down into complex moving parts that illustrate the reality-based struggle of green energy conversion in our world today. Couture's (2023) interview with the developers states that the creators wanted the game to focus on communities that are "ravaged by the industrialization, disasters, and by the effects of the energy transition itself." Tecson (2024) suggests that this game is meant to teach players about environmental sciences, climate change, renewable energy, and the challenges of transitioning to such energy practices.

The majority of reviews on gaming websites have been overtly positive, though some users have noted that the game is challenging and that the win condition is difficult to achieve. Another player mused that one must carefully consider the regions being managed and which card will be most effective, while another player noted that it takes numerous playthroughs to win the game.

Game Principle & Process

The Green New Deal Simulator is a card-based game. Each turn, players have the option to draw a card, skip a card, play a card, or hold a card for later. The player must keep an eye on

their budget meter, the unemployment in each state, the amounts of green energy, fossil energy, and fossil electricity (which can eventually be converted into green energy), and, lastly, the game's progress meter at the top. Should players fail to reach green energy usage within a set period, an authoritarian government takes over the United States, and the game ends. The progress meter alerts the player when their choices lead to the takeover of an authoritarian government.

Examples of cards are High-Speed Rail, which reduces gas consumption and helps with commuting, but also raises unemployment equally across neighboring regions; and Solar Farm, which absorbs energy from the sun to make electricity and is twice as efficient when played in sunny regions. Some cards require a positive budget to play, so players must manage their funding and choose to skip cards that may be less useful to the country's current status (unemployment, green energy amounts per state, etc.) to have a larger budget for the next turn. Some cards, like Pumped Storage Hydropower, do not have a negative side effect, but they can only be played in regions with mountains, which limits where players can activate them. This is a weighted choice, as public transport has other positive effects for the game, but is balanced by the negative repercussions of higher gas use in that region. Players may also be potentially affected by random events such as natural disasters or workers' strikes, which can raise unemployment and set back progress in a particular state. Players must not only manage the region they are trying to produce green energy in, but also all neighboring regions, keeping the entire country in mind to ensure that none of the negative effects are pressuring any region too much.

Players may also play research cards, which improve the qualities and impact of existing cards. For example, players may upgrade solar energy to reduce the cost of installing future solar farms or research fusion energy. Fusion energy is usually discovered too late in the game to ever reach fruition, prompting the player to reflect on whether it is worth playing at all.

Learning Objectives & Educational Fields of Application

The main goal of Green New Deal Simulator is to give an overarching view of how green energy changes could affect the U.S., and give the player insight into the moving pieces of what each policy will affect, though the game's message is not limited to the real-world relation of being set in the United States; these are ideas and principles that can be applied universally across the globe. Rather than just merely installing wind farms, consideration must be given to unemployment, green energy percentages in current and nearby states, where a card and energy type or change would be most effective in a region, and planning to maximize the change. The player learns, through cause-and-effect, the different negative impacts of both green and fossil-fuel technologies. The player also discovers how policy changes can provoke criticism and pushback, and provides an overview of how to manage competing goals in a nation composed of diverse people and regions with specific, varied needs and capabilities. The game offers a nuanced perspective on how green policies may work and details how they

may be achieved. The learning goal of this game is to teach about green energy policies and installations, and to address the potential harms of switching to green energy.

Instructors may find this game helpful to spur discussion about potential green energy sources, the consequences of those changes, and the consequences of failing to mitigate the negative effects of climate change. Students can benefit from multiple playthroughs to revise their strategies and attempt to play the game again with a better outcome. This game encourages multiple playthroughs to streamline attempts at 100% green energy. Students can discuss with one another to learn better strategies and formulate new approaches and ideas for successfully converting the U.S. to green energy through trial and error.

Effectiveness

There have been no studies on the effectiveness of the Green New Deal Simulator's rhetoric in converting the U.S. to green energy. However, the game does help engage players' minds and prompt them to consider creative solutions to a real-world problem humanity faces. It helps students think creatively, decisively, and intuitively about how we can manage our current predicament. The game may help motivate students to engage with these topics in their day-to-day lives and may also help them think more deeply about effective solutions to Earth's problems by learning more about the proposed solutions it offers (Tecson, 2024).

Potentially Problematic Aspects

A potential concern with Green New Deal Simulator is its strong emphasis on clean, green-sourced energy as the core of U.S. energy production. This focus may be interpreted as aligning with left-leaning political perspectives and could unintentionally alienate students or families with differing ideological views. Although clean energy is not inherently partisan, it is frequently associated with progressive rhetoric, which may affect perceptions of neutrality. Additionally, the game's exclusive focus on the United States may limit its relevance for international students from countries with different energy infrastructure, regulations, and environmental contexts.

Reviewer(s): Saskia Sterzl

Sources

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